

A novel approach to copyright protection using watermarking method based on DWT – DCT

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Abstract: Over the last ten years, rapid advancements in the digital global network and digital media technology have made it easier to copy, modify, and share data, such as photographs, video, and audio, across the internet via the world wide web without losing its original quality and in very short periods of time. The protection of multimedia material ownership has been fraught with difficulties. This thesis examines the basics that the map of disparity and watermarking will employ in order to verify that online content is properly owned. To turn binary information into images, a 3D image watermarking technique is presented. When studying methods of image authentication, it is common practice to first convert the original image into smaller blocks and then embed a watermark into each individual block. This is followed by the application of a modification idea to the blocks in order to identify the watermark. In this research, we present a new architecture for DWT-DCT –based digital watermarking systems for images. The technique prevents unauthorized use of digital images by embedding a stealthy watermark into each one. In order to create a picture with a watermark, the original image is first divided into blocks using a Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT), then the watermark is changed and a pseudo–random sequence is generated using Arnold scrambling. Image segmentation, the discrete Fourier transform, and relativity processes all contribute to watermark identification. The Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) technique is used to increase the security of a watermarking algorithm based on image segmentation. The watermark detector is used to detect the watermark. In order to not affect the bit rate, use the choice matrix to extract the picture from the left or right –aligned image. It can be achieved through two unique additions to the detection process, Reverse rendering, and the CRC method. The described technique of reverse returning reduces the decision matrix to a smaller map of disparities. The left picture can be restored to the right image using this disparity reduction. A CRC control is used to identify the image, which detects faults in the message extracted and lowers errors in recognizing the picture (left or right). Moreover, for the simulation’s purpose, MATLAB will be used. The proposed approach is validated using different scenarios and variations in parameters using statistical analysis.

Keywords: DCT, DWT, CRC, Image, Watermarking, Masking, Filtering.

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Introduction

On the media and games markets, 3D digital content is fast growing, but copyright protection measures are still in their infancy. Existing watermarking 3D models are used to hide copyright information and are focused on robustness against possible assaults to delete embedded watermarks. However, no unambiguous auto-protection capable of embedding visible 3D watermarks into the original 3D image while also removing the watermark without causing damage to the 3D host image has yet to be shown in the scientific literature. A removable watermark image is layered over the 3D host, the original image in my suggested technique. It was possible to erase it by encrypting several parameters iconcealedceal watermark. By segmenting the regions across the specified 3D triangle mesh, a 3D watermark is hidden utilizing surface curvatures. By statistically altering the distance between each mesh vertex and the mesh's mass center, the watermark is incorporated in the regions. On the sender side, the presented approach embeds a visible watermark in a 3D host image together with a hidden encrypted message, and then extracts and decrypts the parameters on the receiver side to erase the visual watermark. Copyright and ownership of digital material can be effectively protected by digital watermarking. One of the most pressing issues in modern scientific inquiry is the inability to reliably secure electronic documents. Since the proliferation of Internet-based technology, unauthorized users have found new ways to copy, fake, and spread digital content. Therefore, researchers have explored watermarking methods for a wide range of applications, such as broadcasting, tracking, intellectual property protection, document verification, and copy limitation [1]. Copyright infringement, unauthorized use, replication, and online content theft have all increased along with the widespread uploading and dissemination of electronic information on the Internet. Copyright protection is essential for digital photos since they are valuable resources. However, digital watermarking [2] is a modern and practical method of safeguarding such photographs.

The use of digital watermarking for images has been studied only in a few cases. In recent years, a number of methods have been established for watermark embedding, including the use of algorithms for WM extraction and modification from digital images [3-9]. In general, watermarking can be attacked maliciously, with the goal of erasing or eliminating the encoded WM data, or non-maliciously, through the processes necessary to preserve or distribute the information. Therefore, both algorithmic and mechanical approaches could be used to achieve WM embedding. On the flip side, WM extraction takes place in a variety of alternative settings.

The embedded WM data may be lost if the host information is destroyed by a cyberattack, malicious or otherwise. Therefore, it is possible that a statistical technique will yield superior results than either a programmed or a sequential approach to WM extraction.

Furthermore, DWT's capacity to ease transformation is a major factor in its rising popularity because it considerably improves the security of watermarked digital photos. As shown in [16], the DWT domain takes an image and breaks it down into a series of steps that are executed in order of decreasing resolution. The masking of watermarks with higher intensity during digital photographs increases their endurance. SVD is currently used extensively in the watermarking of digital photographs. SVD keeps the covered image visible and secure against a wide variety of attacks [17, 18]. In recent years, advancements in machine learning (ML) and learning approaches have allowed computers and servers to get closer to using human-level skills. Companies are actively searching for ways to make use of their huge datasets, such as utilizing them as a testing ground for algorithms that may interact with their surroundings in innovative and valuable ways, hence providing insights that have not been discovered before. Deep learning (DL) based neural network (NN) methods have been shown to be effective in resolving a wide range of challenges in fields as diverse as audio signal analysis, image processing, computational linguistics, and natural language processing (NLP) [19-22]. These fields include audio signal analysis, image processing, and natural language processing (NLP).

Research Methodology

Due to the growing popularity of the internet and digital media, it is now possible to effortlessly copy, modify, and distribute multimedia data such as photographs, videos, and audio files across the internet without suffering any discernible degradation in quality. As a result, the problem of producing legitimate multimedia data has become a highly pressing one. The approach that can be used to secure ownership in an efficient manner is known as digital watermarking, and it can be applied to any digital file. Using a method known as digital watermarking, you can encode a small bit of confidential information known as a watermark. During the subsequent stages of the authentication procedure, this watermark may be analyzed or extracted. In principle, every single watermarking system should be able to satisfy the following requirements [1]: (1) perceptual invisible (2) The removal of the watermark should be

exceedingly tough to do without negatively affecting the image quality. (3) Robustness against additional manipulations and attacks.

1.1 Research Aim

The aim of this research is to propose a novel approach to copyright protection using a watermarking method based on enhanced DWT – DCT techniques.

1.1.1 Research Questions

RQ1: How to identify the features to improve the existing image-watermarking model using Enhanced DCT-DWT Approach?

RQ2: How to propose a novel Copyright Protection Using Watermarking Method Based on Enhanced DWT – DCT?

RQ3: How to validate the propose framework using benchmark model?

1.2.1 Research Objectives

RO1: To identify the feature that can efficiently improve the existing copyright protection- Using image-watermarking methods.

RO2: To propose efficient Copyright Protection Using Watermarking Method Based on Enhanced DWT – DCT.

RO3: To validate the proposed framework using a benchmark model.

1.2.2 Contribution to the research

The contribution to this research is listed below:

- ⊙ We identified the features from the literature based on copyright protection using the DWT-DCT method that can efficiently improve the security and the performance of the exist-ing model.
- ⊙ The proposal of an efficient copyright model using an Optimization approach in order to lev-erage the security and performance of the existing work.
- ⊙ Comparative analysis of the existing work.
- ⊙ The design of a novel method for validation and testing our proposed idea.
- ⊙ For the watermarking scheme in this thesis, the quantization technique was used in order to make the system more resistant to JPEG compression attacks.

1.2.3 The following attacks were used to evaluate the system's performance:

- Salt and Pepper Noise Addition.
- Gaussian Noise Addition.
- Median Filtering.
- Blurring Filter.
- Salt and Pepper Noise Addition.
- Sharpening Filter.
- Histogram Equalization.
- Cropping.
- JPEG Compression.

Background Theory

In recent years, three–dimensional visuals and movies have grown in popularity among general audiences. The introduction of 3D movies in 2003 sparked this desire. 3D displays and multimedia systems were introduced as the technology became more widely used and got into the business world as more films kept being released, this medium continues to grow in popularity.

An example of where three dimensions display was used is during the 50th anniversary of the British Broadcasting Company (BBC) that was recently released. Also, an episode of the popular television series Doctor Who was released in 3D and the experience is really thrilling.

Converting existing 2D media into a 3D format is the most active field in 3D display technology presently. However, mainstream media outlets like "Netflix" and "Hulu" have yet to adopt 3D content. As 3D content–encoding technology advances and its popularity develops, it is projected that internet movie networks will adopt it in the near future. The protection of copyright holders is critical for the continued development of this technology. If something like this happens, while copyright protection is a hot topic in academia, 3D media is still in its infancy. Copyright protection can be accomplished in a variety of ways. Because of the widespread dissemination of services across Internet networks, transaction tracking is the most widely used. A good example is "Safari Books Online." When a user buys an eBook, the transaction contains concealed information that can be used to identify the individual. This encryption is used to determine if a user is malevolent or not. On a peer–to–peer network, the user's information is shared. If the user is malicious, he or she will be detected and their access would be revoked. As 3D material becomes more popular and more widely distributed, measures to safeguard their contents will become increasingly important. Usually used to identify the copyright owner, binary or greyscale graphics are employed. This strategy is useful in cases where proving copyright ownership is difficult, such as an image of a well–known area. Transaction Tracking Systems are used to track and protect the copyright of material being sent from a database to a user while also encoding a unique user identity (watermark).

These solutions are advantageous when no proof of ownership is necessary, such as when a popular film is involved. Instead, these platforms allow users to download copyrighted content if they are registered. Identifiers that are unique to the users are commonly found in acquired content.

Transaction tracking is beneficial in that it allows service providers to efficiently distribute their material to end–users while avoiding fraudulent consumers. If criminal individuals redistribute content on a peer –to –peer networks, the copyright owner can track them down thanks to a unique identifier contained in the media. The behavior of a transaction tracking system where a copyright owner sends content to two distributors and once a malicious person uploads the content to a peer–to–peer network, the first distributor sets up a transaction tracking system. The distributor has the ability to track down the problematic user.

2.1 3D Vision

2.1.1 Human Binocular Vision

The technique through which the human brain understands depth is still a mystery. Due to the intricacy of the human visual system, this thesis will only cover the essentials of the subject. Dual pictures are useful

For –depth estimation, they are not the sole option. The size of known items, such as trees, animals, and people, and the convergence of parallel lines, such as highways, are two examples. These methods are simple to use with human vision, but they are more difficult to compute.

Figure 1: Examples for (a) Diplopia Cause, and (b) Binocular Rivalry Cause

Hawkins [4] points up a few visual occurrences that are related to stereoscopic displays. Stereopsis is the fusion of two pictures perceived by the eyes into a single image including non –quantitative depth information. Assume the merger of the two images is unsuccessful. Diplopia, in which two ghost pictures are formed, and Binocular rivalry, in which an image from one eye is repressed in favor of an image from the other, generally leading to an oscillation between the two images, are the causes in that scenario. Diplopia occurs when the eyes are unable to converge on an object, such as when it is too close to the seeing center. Binocular rivalry occurs when each eye receives a separate image that cannot be combined into a single image.

Figure 2: (a) zero parallax, (b) negative parallax, and (c) positive parallax

2.1.2 Binocular Vision Image Capture

The disparate positions of an object's pictures formed by the left and right eye provide humans the ability to experience depth. These images are utilized in 3D Display technology to create the illusion of depth on a flat surface. To create this effect, left and right pictures are projected onto the monitor to create a single image. When dealing with simulated depth, Grinberg et al. Pointed out that the following concerns may arise:

1. Image Acquisition: how the image will be captured in each eye,
2. Image Display Tool: The captured images are isolated and displayed on the right eye

Image acquisition takes into account a number of factors, including the correct distance from the camera, the angle between the image capture planes, and the lens offset. Images should never be captured for a single viewing experience in order to choose the best parameters for each system. They are frequently shown on multiple surfaces and seen in varied situations. For that reason, a set of assumptions must be developed to simplify the procedure and create a near-optimal viewing state for the most prevalent cases. It is worth noting that the assumptions are based on a single flat rectangular display surface. The first assumption is that the recording and display environments are identical. That is to say, the visuals on the left and right are merely scaled versions of the original recording.

2.1.3 Image formats and Compression

Any 3 –D scene is captured by N cameras, where N is greater than one. In recent years, more complex systems with 8 or 16 cameras have been implemented.

Although research into improving and expanding this technology is ongoing, it is still a few years away from being introduced to the general public. As a result, this section is just for Image formats with $N = 2$. There are three main formats for showing photographs.

In an interlaced GIF, the images are vertically interlaced while keeping the original image's vertical and horizontal proportions. The most significant disadvantage of this method is that it discards half of the vertical pixel data. The last compression method is colored anaglyph, in which each image is converted to a color anaglyph and then concatenated. After that, it is compressed using Industry –standard formats. The fundamental downside of this format is that it suffers from color loss, resulting in poor compression results; yet, it is perfect for glyph display technology. To learn about a few additional 3D image compression approaches, keep reading. and while there are a variety of ways, both sources agree that disparity maps and depth maps provide the optimum compression ratios.

Due to the changing nature of disparity vectors, disparity map rendering is a limited method that will require changes. The user cannot alter the 3D depth of disparity maps, which is the second disadvantage. When compared to depth

maps, the key advantage of disparity maps is the higher compression ratio. This is because each image's depth values, which range from 0 to 255, are collected.

On the other hand, a depth map image can change the user's perception of depth. Depth maps were not chosen due to a few issues. The first disadvantage is that more large data is necessary. The second disadvantage is that the computational complexity increases. Due to their extraordinarily high compression ratios, disparity maps were used in this thesis.

Assume we have an RGB 360 by 280-, or 100,800-pixel image to compare the three formats when image compression is taken into account. The first image format (Stereo Pair) requires 604,800 bytes of storage. The second format (Disparity Maps) requires a total of 302400 bytes for the picture and 50400 bytes for the disparity map for a total of 352800 bytes. Finally, 403200 bytes are required for the third format (Depth Map).

When the disparity values surpass the 255 restrictions, such as when the image has a very high resolution, there are several exceptions. Taking off the DC bias and dividing the disparity values according to the GCD would be a simple approach.

Only a few bytes would be required to store the bias and GCD value. If a satisfactory viewing experience is required, the maximum disparity value cannot exceed 3% of the image size when employing disparity Map-based rendering algorithms.

2.2 Background information

The fundamentals of image processing and watermarking systems are explained in this section. It gives a quick run-down of the two models that these systems employ. Watermark pattern synthesis, embedding and detection methods finally, and image processing methods will be discussed, with an emphasis on image processing conversions.

The simplest basic watermarking model effectively depicts how a watermarking technique works: a message is added to work and then delivered. A message is decoded once it arrives. While the model is not used in practice, it does aid in the demonstration of some of the earlier definitions. This section discusses two watermarking models that can be used. The first is a model of communication. It is a term that is widely used to describe a system's behavior. The dashed lines represent components of the model that may or may not exist.

During the transmission phase, however, the cover work could be changed due to channel characteristics or a hostile user's attack. The created model assumes that an attack has two elements: an attack block and an attack signal, for simplicity. In the case of compression, for example, the attack block is the compression algorithm, and the attack signal is the compression parameter.

The signal is then sent to the detector of the receiver. The message is output by the decoder based on its best guess of the message that is contained. While this communication model works for many watermarking systems, it ignores the fact that the embedded is knowledgeable. In the encoding stage, an informed embedded accepts the cover work as input and uses some of it.

The models aid in the testing of watermarking methods under various threats. However, when it comes to defining the embedding and detecting procedures, they fall short. A geometric model is utilized to quantify the behavior of these two processes. Each vector in this domain represents a piece of cover art (an image). The media space is what it is called. This means that every image is an N–N–Dimensional Vector, with each pixel representing a dimension. The media space is a discrete rectilinear lattice with a tiny enough quantization of pictures to be interpreted as a continuous rectilinear lattice.

2.2.1 Watermarking models

The most basic watermarking model is described, which successfully explains how a watermarking method works: a message is added to work and then transferred. A message is decoded once it arrives. While the model is not used in practice, it does aid in the demonstration of some of the earlier definitions. This section discusses two watermarking models that can be found. The first is a model of communication. It is a term that is widely used to describe a system's behavior.

The model depicted in the diagram assumes that the message is transmitted to the encoder first, and then mapped into a watermark pattern layer. This layer is usually the same type and size as the cover work's target region. After that, a watermark pattern layer is instantly applied to the cover artwork and delivered. In ideal circumstances, the sent cover work arrives undamaged and unaltered.

During the transmission phase, however, the cover work could be changed due to channel characteristics or a hostile user's attack. The created model assumes that an attack has two elements: an attack block and an attack signal, for simplicity. In the case of compression, for example, the attack block is the compression algorithm, and the attack signal is the compression parameter. The signal is then sent to the detector of the receiver. The message is output by the decoder based on its best guess of the message that is contained. While this communication model works for many watermarking systems, it ignores the fact that the embedded is knowledgeable. In the encoding stage, an informed embedded accepts the cover work as input and uses some of it.

The models supplied to aid in the testing of watermarking techniques against various attackers. However, when it comes to defining the embedding and detecting procedures, they fall short. A geometric model is utilized to quantify the behavior of these two processes.

Each vector in this domain represents a piece of cover art (an image). The media space is what it is called. This means that every image is an N-Dimensional Vector, with each pixel representing a dimension. The media space is a discrete rectilinear lattice with a tiny enough quantization of pictures to be interpreted as a continuous rectilinear lattice.

When it comes to embedding and detection, the media space model is applied. Although this model is utilized in three terms that are defined here. First, an N-Dimensional hypersphere centered on the cover work vector where picture distortions are under acceptable quality bounds is the region of acceptable fidelity. Second, embedding disruption refers to the whole system distortion caused by the embedding process. Finally, within the media space, Detection Regions arise when the detector can detect a watermark within the message.

2.2.2 Watermarking Process

While some watermarking systems include the watermark directly in the image, others convert the image to a new domain. The marking space is another name for the domain transform. The marking space is often utilized to make the watermarking procedure easier or to improve the system's detection capabilities. Spatial and transform domains are the two most common marking spaces. The spatial domain watermarking strategy works by modifying the provided pixel information in order to save the data in a way that is undetectable to the system. Using the Least Significant Bits to store data is an example of this. However, change domain approaches invert the process by transforming the pixels into a different representation and adding the watermark to that domain.

Despite the strengths of both systems, transform domain embedding is used in this thesis. While spatial approaches have a larger storage capacity and a lower computational cost, they are also exceedingly vulnerable and cannot withstand attacks. Transform domain watermarking was chosen to achieve the robustness goal. To make the watermarking analysis easier, the provided cover work will be presumed to be in its marking space already (underwent a domain transformation). The transform procedure is also assumed to follow the Discrete Cosine Transform in this thesis (DCT). For a variety of reasons, DCT is the transformation of choice. DC, Low-frequency, mid-frequency, and high-frequency elements are all included. By selecting the embedding region, it is possible to balance the fidelity and robustness restrictions. Low-frequency watermark insertion allows for greater assault resistance when embedded within DCT marking space, but it degrades image quality.

Embedding in the high-frequency zones, on the other hand, provides lesser attack resistance but higher image quality. The watermark is applied to the middle-frequency bands in this thesis to achieve a balance between the two. This thesis describes the watermarking addition procedure and assumes that the provided information has already been transformed into its marking space (DCT).

2.2.3 Watermark Detection

While there are many other ways to watermark identification, this thesis chose Correlation-based detection because it requires fewer input files. Normally, the value of the correlation is compared to a specified threshold value (T) to decide the bit that is saved after a correlation is done on the marked cover work.

The dot product of the two vectors is the value of the 22 correlations. The constant value of w_{pf} can be read as an orthogonal projection of the cover work vector onto the reference pattern vector if w_{pf} is constant. When comparing a set of vectors to a threshold value, the set of vectors that surpass the threshold value will be on one side of a plane perpendicular to w_{pf} . This boundary is a $(p - 1)$ hyperplane, implying that the embedding process is two-state. Unfortunately, this detection system has a wide detection region, which leads to a higher proportion of false positives.

Figure 3: Framework for the embedding process

The normalized correlation is the second correlation method employed. The main advantage of this method is that it removes the correlation's dependence on magnitude. Changes in brightness or contrast, in other words, have a lower impact on the detection process and can be regarded as a dot-product operation. When the reference pattern is orthonormal to the cover work, the decision boundary for the NC correlation is a $(p - 1)$ dimensional hyper-cone, according to the preceding equation. The image will have no bearing on the detection procedure. If the reference pattern is orthonormal, the results are correlated. The flaws in the preceding designs are addressed in this plan. As a result, in this thesis, the CC correlation is applied.

2.2.4 Watermark Pattern

The Key and Pseudo Noise Generator are two components that are used in the majority of watermark pattern-generating techniques. PNG output is semi-predictable because the critical value is usually sent as an initial seed. The receiver can reproduce the reference pattern with a single value using this added key. This strategy is greatly influenced by Spread Spectrum Communication. SSC spreads a small baseband signal across numerous frequencies, making it more difficult to detect an attack. Typically, pseudo-noise sequences produced from PNG are used for this propagation [22]. The output of the PN sequence should have a zero mean and a unit standard deviation.

The spreading sequence indicated above suffers from low energy levels. As the required sequence increases in size, the energy spreads over the p values. This thesis uses pseudo-random binary sequences to address this problem. Various binary sequences exist within SSC. The key is used to determine the initial state of the linear feedback shift registers in these sequences. "The primary properties of PN binary sequences are

- Balance: A sequence of $(2^n - 1)$ bits, should have (2^{n-1}) ones and $(2^{n-1} - 1)$ zeros, and
- Autocorrelation: Autocorrelation of the sequence should be 1, whenever $n = 0$, and 1^{n-1} otherwise.

When utilizing SSC, these qualities make PN binary sequences particularly helpful. While there are many other PN binary sequences, m-sequences are used in this thesis. Because the watermark embedding procedure employed in this thesis only requires one watermark pattern, this is the rationale. The m-sequences generator is the simplest technique of PN creation that fits the requirements of this thesis. A polynomial list was employed for the LFSR polynomials.

2.2.5 Image Processing Concepts

Some image-processing approaches are employed in this thesis to aid in the watermarking process. In this section, we will talk about format conversion. The color format of an image is changed from RGB to YCbCr before it is converted into its media space. When the watermark is placed in this domain, the luma information is stored in the Y channel, which results in less distortion. In this study, the Y-y-channel is handled as the cover work.

2.2.6 DCT Transforms

The DCT is a well-known frequency transform that is frequently used in image compression. JPEG compression is the most widely used compression method that employs this transform. The transform is a specific subset of the DFT that discards phase information in favor of amplitude information. Because of its application with compression methods, this transform was chosen for this system. We can counteract some of the impacts of compression, which is one of the most typical watermark attacks.

The DCT and inverse DCT equations supplied are a subset of the typical DCT equations. Normally, the DCT can accommodate asymmetrical block sizes in which the number of elements in the x and y directions are not equal. However, only symmetrical-sized blocks are used in this thesis. As a result, the DCT equation represents the intended use.

2.2.7 Quantization

For the watermarking scheme in this thesis, quantization is required. It is done to make the system more resistant to JPEG compression attacks. Following the DCT transform, the DCT steps are quantized.

The quantized DCT block and the quantization matrix is q. It is crucial to notice, however, that the division and multiplication. As a result, the quantization process is carried out according to elements rather than the matrix. This algorithm's quantization matrix is the same as that used in JPEG compression, and it is available below. The intended block sizes in this thesis are 8 by 8.

16	11	10	16	24	40	51	61
12	12	14	19	26	58	60	55
14	13	16	24	40	57	69	56
14	17	22	29	51	87	80	62
18	22	37	56	68	109	103	77
24	35	55	64	81	104	113	92
49	64	78	87	103	121	120	101
72	92	95	98	112	100	103	99

2.2.8 Zig-Zag Scan-lines

Zig-Zag Distortion is a method of reorganizing the two-dimensional DCT transform from lowest to highest frequency bands. This transformation is used to reduce the amount of space required for JPEG compression. It is, however, easier to embed the watermark into the middle frequency bands of the image by transforming the DCT transform of the image into a one-dimensional vector. As a result, it can assist in achieving the ideal balance of resiliency and distortion.

Figure 4: Zig-Zag Scan-line

Literature Survey

An overview of 3D watermarking will be offered in this chapter. Section 3.1 will provide some of the standard stereoscopic image pair watermarking approaches from the literature. Unfortunately, because this is the least popular of the three formats, the information offered will be limited. Section 3.2 will discuss the various watermarking strategies for depth map –based photos. Finally, Section 3.3 will look into watermarking strategies for disparity –based images, which are used in this thesis.

3.1 Stereoscopic Image Pair Watermarking

The work in [24] proposes that embedding decisions should be based on the image's smoothness. To embed the information (binary message), both images are divided into 8 by 8 non –overlapping blocks; these blocks are then converted to the DCT marking space. Let $B_{(l)}^n$ and $B_{(r)}^n$ represent the n^t block for the left and right image, respectively. Once the blocks are in their marking space (frequency domain), the total energy of each block is calculated for both sets. Using the calculated energy value, a decision is made regarding the smoothness of each block by comparing the energy level of the block to the average energy level of all blocks both images. If the value is greater, the value is regarded non –smooth; otherwise, the value is deemed smooth. Vector R is built using the smoothness of the bricks. By comparing the smoothness decisions of $B_{(l)}^n$ and $B_{(r)}^n$ a value of one or zero is stored in $R(n)$, with one recorded if the two blocks have the same smoothness choice and zero stored if they do not. The watermarking procedure begins once the (n) matrix is completed. Assume the value in the R matrix corresponds to the binary value to be saved. In that situation, n blocks are not modified, and a value of zero is kept in (n) , a matrix that tracks picture modifications.

If (n) is equal to zero, the DC coefficient is as below:

Following formula: $Q = \left\lfloor \frac{DC}{S} \right\rfloor$

If Q is an odd number, the following formula is used to calculate the new DC coefficient

Value: $= Q + 1 - b$, the value to be stored. In the absence of it, the following formula is

used: $DC = Q \cdot S + b$. One is stored in if the first block was quantized (n) ; otherwise, a zero value is retained. An error message will be displayed once all of the blocks have been processed. Inverse DCT is used to recombine the blocks into whole pictures. The modification matrix, (n) , and the parameter S are saved and will be used to reverse the watermark and prove ownership of the image in the future. The information in [24] was embedded by relying on the relationship between the two images. This approach is similar to the work reported in [25], in which the relationship between the two frames is employed for embedding and the depth information between the images. The suggested watermarking system starts by determining the global discrepancy. The global disparity is comparable to the local discrepancy discussed in Section 2. However, we are particularly interested in the mode of the disparity map. Dotted lines depict each camera's area of vision.

The worldwide disparity is used to identify these regions. This value is saved as a key (k_1) , and the luminance layer of the common region is divided into 8 by 8 blocks for another marking space transformed into the DCT domain. The Watson vision model is used to calculate the quantization error strength for the left and right pictures, w_L and the message to be embedded is scrambled and stored in a single DCT coefficient (2nd row, 3rd column) for extra security. The bits are embedded in the images using the formula below if $-R \leq 0$:

$$(1) R^1 = R + a_1 \cdot |L - R| - c_1 \cdot w_R \cdot (2b - 1)$$

$$(2) L^1 = L + a_2 \cdot |L - R| - c_2 \cdot w_R \cdot (2b - 1)$$

In the absence of it, the following equations are used:

$$(1) R^1 = R + a_3 \cdot |L - R| - c_3 \cdot w_R \cdot (2b - 1)$$

$$(2) L^1 = L + a_4 \cdot |L - R| - c_4 \cdot w_R \cdot (2b - 1)$$

Where a and c are weighted coefficients chosen to ensure $L' > R'$ If the stored bit (b) is 1. The work [26] employs a quantized disparity map to split the image into three distinct layers (background, intermediate, and foreground). The extracted disparity map is quantified into three levels for this layering technique. The disparity map is extracted by employing the LL (Low –Pass, Decimation, and then Low –Pass) sub –bands of the picture. The images on the left and right when images are modified using the discrete wavelet transform, these sub –bands are obtained (DWT). Finally, the watermark is embedded in the right image's HL (corresponding to the image that goes through High –Pass, Decimation, and then Low –Pass), LH (corresponding to the image that goes through Low –Pass, Decimation, and then High –Pass), and HH (corresponding to the image that goes through High –Pass, Decimation, and then High –Pass) sub –bands. The embedding operations involve using the quantized disparity map to generate three distinct masks, each of which corresponds to a different sub –bands of the DWT. Certain sub –bands regions are ignored by using masks.

The remaining sub –bands regions are then quantized using one of the following uniforms quantizes:

$$(1) Q! =s \cdot \Delta + d!$$

$$(2) Q! =s! \cdot m!! \cdot \Delta + d2$$

Where \boxed{Q} is the quantize for bit 0 or bit 1, and s_i is an unmasked DWT sub –bands coefficient. (LH, HL, and HH), is the quantization 4 step, and d is a security key. Following the embedding following the reversal of the DWT process, the sub –bands masking is reversed. This approach only embeds the information in the correct image. This scheme's extraction process is identical to that of embedding; however, following sub –bands masking, the system attempts to determine which quantization process was employed and makes a bit decision. This analysis is carried out by passing the retrieved coefficient through Q_0 and subtracting the quantization output from the extracted vector. The Q_0 quantize was employed if the absolute value was less than! A side than that, the Q_1 quantize was employed.

3.2 Depth Map Image Watermarking

The necessity for the watermark to survive 3D warping is the main problem in producing watermarks for Depth –based image formats. The 3D warping method transfers pixels along the horizontal axis to create two images with a sense of depth on the left and right. There is no guarantee that the watermark will remain in the output photos due to these horizontal movements. To address this issue, [27] suggests a novel solution that embeds the watermark in the image's noise. This watermarking system is based on two principles: (1) The histogram of image noise is zero, And (2) 3D Warping of the Center Image transfers information only horizontally, according to the mean Laplacian distribution. The extraction of the noise picture from the center view kicks off the embedding procedure. After that, the extracted noise layer is divided into k noise segments horizontally. A Gaussian zero –mean distribution is used to generate the watermark pattern. The Gaussian mean is then shifted according to the watermark element to be embedded, with a positive shift for a value of 1 and a negative shift otherwise. The embedding process can be defined by the following equation:

$SWix, = N^0, x, y + w (i) (x, y)$, where is the scaling factor, which is determined by the visibility of noise and observable depth difference. The extracted noise will be combined with the shifted noise vector. In [28] a different 3D video watermarking scheme is presented, which exploits some of the depth map characteristics. The first principle that it makes use of is the hidden pixel. When the left and right view images are rendered, there is a possibility that pixels will occupy the same location. This watermarking scheme identifies these locations and treats them as highly weighted embedding positions. It also considers some unique properties unique to 3D video content (z –motion), omitted in the current discussion.

The embedding process in this thesis uses spatial embedding.

This relationship can be defined through the following equation

$x, y = Ftx, y+at x, y \cdot wt(x, y)$. t Weight function in this system is not constant, for its value varies based on a Human Visual Model, Hidden Pixels and the Z-motion.

On the other hand, [29] solved the watermarking problem by embedding the watermark in the Left Image, Center Image, and Right Image. The system proposed in this [29] creates three orthogonal watermark patterns, which will each be embedded in a single view (Left, Center, or Right). The system begins by splitting the image into N by N blocks. Each block is then selected, and two views are rendered (Left and Right). If the number of holes in the image exceeds a predetermined threshold (holes are a side effect of hidden pixels), then the block is embedded with information. The embedding process begins by embedding the center block with the center reference pattern based on the following equation:

$$s + (\alpha \cdot b - \lambda \cdot s') \cdot w_{patte(e)} \text{ where } s' \text{ Is a scaling factor.}$$

After the center block is embedded, the left view is re-synthesized from the watermarked center block and embedded using the same formula but using the left watermark pattern. The rendering process is reversed so that a double watermarked image center now exists. Finally, the straight view is synthesized and watermarked with the right pattern; the rendering process is then reversed.

Under normal viewing conditions, the embedded watermark is invisible. However, whenever the viewing condition is changed, the watermark becomes visible. A simple example of this is invisible ink, where the ink cannot be seen under normal viewing conditions. However, when it is exposed to UV light, the watermark becomes visible. The watermark proposed in [30] embeds an image invisible during standard rendering conditions. However, when one of the rendering parameters is changed, the Watermark becomes visible.

3.3 Disparity Map Image Watermarking

This system begins by calculating the disparity map between the Left and Right Image for the Right Image while creating a one-dimensional left vector using a zig-zag sequence. This zig-zag sequence is re-arranged into a 2D image creating a degraded left image. Afterward, the Fractional Fourier Transform (FrFT) is performed. To embed the watermark, the SVD (singular value decomposition) is used on the disparity map, yielding FrFT output. The SVD transform breaks an image into three separate matrices. The diagonal matrix from the decomposition of the disparity matrix is added to the diagonal matrix of the FrFT decomposition using

$$\text{The following formula: } \Sigma_w = \Sigma_{LeftDegraded} + \alpha \Sigma_{Dispari} .$$

Using the diagonal matrix, Σ_{wm} and the two other matrices generated from FrFT decomposition, the process is reversed to produce a watermarked degraded left image. This is followed by reversing the 2D degradation of the zig-zag Scan line, resulting in a watermarked left image. The watermark detection process is similar to the embedding process. However, the transforms are performed on the watermarked and non-watermarked left images.

$$\text{Thus we have } \Sigma_w = \Sigma_{LeftDegraded} - \alpha \Sigma_{Dispari} .$$

The first location is in the right image before the disparity estimation, and the second location is in the disparity map after the disparity estimation. The system embedded the information using the

Protect method. Protect is a hybrid method, which treats watermarking as an optimization problem. The system encodes and decodes the message. Based on the detected errors in the message, the pattern is modified and re-embedded. By iterating through the solution, the system will converge on an embedded signal capable of being recovered. [35] and [36] propose a novel watermarking scheme while exploring the benefits of different frequency domain transformations. In addition, they evaluate different disparity map estimation techniques. This section will begin with a discussion of the embedding process used in [35] and [36] and continues by specifying the transforms and disparity map cost functions used. The embedding process begins by transforming the Right Image into a frequency domain, after which the values are quantized. For simplicity, assume the transform is one-dimensional.

This would yield a vector $RI = \{RI_0, RI_1, \dots, RI_M\}$. Equivalently, the watermark Transform coefficients is $W = \{W_0, W_1, \dots, W_N\}$, where N is smaller than M . The watermark coefficients are then re ordered using a random seed. Afterward, the coefficients are used to replacesome coefficients of the image, resulting in a new vector in the form of

$RI = \{RI_0, RI_1, \dots, T_0, T_1, \dots, T_i, T_{i+1}, \dots, T_N, \dots, RI_M\}$, where $T_i = RI_i + \alpha |RI_i| W$. The reason that the middle coefficients are replaced is simple. If the lower frequency values were modified, the effect on the system would be too great. On the other hand, if the lower coefficients are replaced the watermark would be fragile to compression attacks. Afterward, the inverse transformation is executed. The disparity calculation is performed, and the left image and the disparity map are transmitted. Using the random seed key, the watermark can be extracted and reordered to restore the initial embedding mark, but only after the right image is reconstructed, using the left image and the disparity map.

3.4 Limitations of Existing Work

There exist watermarking methods that are beneficial to the image watermarking, but there exist some issue related to these techniques such as poor attack resistant, noise issue and latency. Moreover, as the existing system designed in [24], for decoded it needs to arrive both left and right side of the image to be watermark embedded. In other case, the contents will be lost. Which leads to security issue during the transfer of information and can lead to false information. Such kind of shortcoming also exist in model presented by [25]. However, the work in [25] stored polar values in the image while it is possible, in theory, to extract the watermark from a single image by using the original lost image. Moreover, the researcher did not explored much about the security issue related to such model this would introduce more information to be stored at the detector to help extract the watermark.

The work in [27] designed and follow watermark –embedding feature. Moreover, such kind of approach is capable of detecting the image from the left, right, and center image. This problem is shared by the work presented in [28], where larger watermark patterns are used. The work presented in [31] aims to limit the effects of watermark on the viewing experience and suffers from the same limitations as the system presented in [28], which are large watermark patterns and low bitrates. While [29] proposed embedding the watermark in all three versions of the image, the main drawback of the advantage of this approach is its scalability. The amount of information that can be embedded within an image decreases as the image size increases. This issue is caused by the design of the watermarking scheme, which renders the images to embed the desired information. The second limitation of this watermarking scheme is that it cannot differentiate between watermarked and non –watermarked blocks. [30], on the other hand, attempts to embed information within the watermark by distorting the image in specific rendering environments. This approach would be effective for detecting copyright holders; however, due to the unique properties of the watermarking scheme, it is incapable of embedding information from a malicious user.

The work in [26] proposes storing information in the right image's watermark. This watermarking scheme prevents the detector from retrieving any information from the left image and relies solely on the right image to be transmitted for detection. However, the work in [26] stored information in the disparity map, and this information can only be detected once the correct image is rendered, whereas it is stored in the disparity map in [33] and [34]. The information cannot be retrieved from the left or right image due to the disparity map being used as the cover work.

Proposed Method

In this section, will try to explain and present the realization of our proposed system. This chapter aims at expanding the theory presented before in the preceding chapters and presents a watermarking system for the 3D Disparity – based images.

4.1 System Overview

Figure 5: Proposed Framework

The whole system is divided into three tiers for ease of use. The embedding layer, for example, is in charge of inserting the watermark into the left picture. The disparity map and the watermarked left image are found in the transmission layer. The detecting layer is the final layer. The embedding layer is further divided into two parts: (1) Pre –processing and (2) Embedding. The disparity map of the images, as well as the total distortion that will result from the rendering process, must be determined prior to the embedding procedure. This data is utilized to create a decision matrix that will be used by the embedded. This Pre –processing aids in increasing the bit recovery rate of the message.

The embedding method takes the information provided and embeds the message into the image after these two jobs are completed. The information is delivered over the transmission layer after the embedding procedure is complete. The content is utilized once the information has arrived at its intended destination. The detector can identify the criminal user if the protected content is redistributed via unapproved channels.

The disparity map is created as the initial step in this process. To build a disparity map of the image, the disparity map employs the reduction technique. Note that the disparity map's values vary, and the search range must be limited to 3% of the image width. After the disparity map estimation process is completed, the disparity map goes through some filtering. The filtering step improves the smoothness of the disparity map, resulting in a better –rendered image. It also improves the system's ability to endure attacks by increasing the disparity map's resistance to filtering attacks.

The removal of image cropping is the key issue in the disparity map technique detailed thus far. Certain picture portions are ineligible for disparity estimate due to the nature of the disparity maps. To address this issue, the images are zero padded, with padding equal to the windowing function. This step aids in the removal of cropping on the image's edges. The cushioning is removed after this stage is completed. Two disparity maps are created to overcome the search range's constraints. The first map is created by using the reference image on the left, while the second map uses the reference image on the right. The two maps are then blended using a “winner –take –all” strategy.

The decision matrix is used to forecast the image's gaps and hidden pixels. When two pixels in the rendered image occupy the same space location, this happens. In the rendered image, one of these pixels will be lost. In the context of watermarking, this information loss will result in the embedded watermark losing its power.

Figure 6: Proposed System Architecture

To assist predict where these occurrences will occur, a prediction process is performed. A faux –left picture is created first. The dimensions of this fake image are the same as the actual image, and the values rise along the x –axis. Normally, pixel values are limited to 255 per pixel, however in the false –Image, this limit is eliminated to assure pixel uniqueness. For a faux –left view, these images are defined as $I(x, y)$ and for a faux –right view, $I_{GR}(x, y)$.

This image, together with the created disparity map, is transmitted to the image renderer. This creates two fake photos, one on the left and one on the right, which proceed through the algorithm's steps. This algorithm is a tweaked version of the disparity map estimation technique.

4.2 Message processing

The message formatting is critical to the system's operation. The storage capacity varies from image to image due to the nature of the proposed method. However, the number of accessible blocks usually determines this figure. Let N_A be the number of embedding places that are available. The total number of bits that can be stored is defined by the following equation:

$$S_M = N_A - P \cdot k - C_S$$

Where S_M is the total number of accessible bits, k represents the convolutional code rate, C_S represents the CRC code size, and P represents the polarity header. Because the decision matrix is volatile, the value of available bits differs from image to image. The initial P bits of the system have no function in the detecting process, as can be seen from the structure. Some watermark attacks, however, cause the embedded message's polarity to be inverted. The polarity header is included at the start of the message to help combat this issue. A reference mark is provided in this manner to aid in the identification of the embedded message's polarity. The message's second half is made up of two parts.

The image is divided into 8x8 square chunks to incorporate multiple bits messages. A single bit is contained in each of these blocks. The concealed pixel disparity map information is used before the embedding procedure to determine which regions should be embedded and which should be excluded. The HPDM (Hidden Pixel Disparity Map) is divided into sections. Each block is examined to confirm that it is free of holes and that all discrepancy values within it are the same. This eliminates various types of disparity map issues while also ensuring that no hidden pixels exist. This matrix should be saved because it will be crucial in the process of detecting.

4.3 Embedding Process

The approach of embedding, the image is initially divided into chunks of equal size. The matrix is used to quantize each of these blocks, which is then followed by a DCT frequency transform. The zig-zag scan-line transformation is applied to these variables. The middle-frequency bands are selected after the zig-zag transformation, and the watermark pattern is applied using the equation shown. The mid-frequency vector is reinserted into the image's zig-zag scan-line after the watermark pattern is applied. This, along with the quantization and DCT transform, is reversed, yielding a watermarked block.

4.4 Watermark Extraction Process

The watermark extraction process divides the incoming image into blocks, converting the frequency matrix into a vector once more before selecting the middle-frequency bands. A choice concerning the embedded bit is made using the correlation coefficient formula and the threshold equation provided. The decision matrix is used to figure out which blocks have embedded bits in them. The first P bits (polarity header) are extracted if they follow the required format after all of the information from all blocks has been taken. The mechanism then advances to the next stage of the watermarking procedure. Otherwise, the extracted bits' polarity is inverted. Following the decoding procedure, the remaining bits are decoded using a Viterbi decoder. The final C_s bits have been eliminated.

4.5 3D Image Decoder

The detecting method is slightly more sophisticated due to the nature of 3D rendering. The detection procedure as a whole is depicted in this diagram. When the detector receives a picture, it is unable to distinguish between the left and right views. As a result, the system contains two methods for extracting watermarks. The first path assumes that the picture received is the left image, whereas the second path assumes that the image received is the right image. The right path reverses the decision matrix's rendering process, which is the fundamental difference between the two paths. After that, the above-mentioned watermark extraction procedure is conducted. If one of the pathways states that the extraction process has completed successfully, the user is notified.

4.6 Practical Realization of Rendering

While the rendering method accurately depicted the theoretical approach concept, it suffers from actual implementation issues. The suggested approach addresses this issue by altering the rendering process to better reflect the nature of the difference between the two image pixels. This is accomplished by splitting the rendering process into phases with $(d_{max} + 1)$ disparity values. Each of these processes necessitates the creation of a mask, with m_i serving as the mask. Each of these masks represents a different disparity value; for example, mask m_1 represents all pixels in the image that will experience a one-pixel horizontal shift.

```

1   Let  $D(k, j)$  be the disparity map
2   Let  $I_R$  be the rendered image
3   for  $m = 0 \dots d_{max}$ 
4   for  $j = 1 \dots y_{max}$ 
5   for  $k = 1 \dots x_{max}$ 
6   if  $(k, j)$  equals  $m$ 
7    $I_R(k, j) = I(k, j)$ 
8   end if
9   end for
10  end for
11  end for
    
```

The system shifts the pixels of the image one layer at a time after producing the masks, starting with mask m_0 and increasing until mask m_{dm} is reached. For the following reasons, it is a significantly more practical manifestation of the System: (1) The rendering is more realistic, and (2) the output image is unaffected by the rendering direction. To expand on the first benefit, a foreground pixel with a greater disparity value is significantly more likely to occupy a pixel location than a background pixel with a lower disparity value. Far more realistic scenes are created by generating the background first and then enabling the foreground to replace the pixel. Concerning the second.

4.7 Proposed Algorithms

Algorithm is designed for disparity map and pixel that are hidden inside the image for copyright protection.

The algorithm is explained step by step as below:

Algorithm: Combined Map Addition of Disparity map And Hidden Pixel Map

```

1   for  $j = 1 \dots y_{max}$ 
2   for  $k = 1 \dots x_{max}$ 
3    $D_F(k, j) = \{1\}$ 
4   for all value of  $d$  in set  $S$ 
5   if  $I(k, j)$  equals  $I_{GR}(k, j - d)$ 
6    $D_F(k, j) = d$ 
7   end if
8   end for
9   end for
10  end for
    
```

4.8 Assumptions and Observations

There were a few assumptions made in the system design throughout this thesis. Many of these factors influenced the design decision for the proposed system. This section opens with a discussion of some of these assumptions, which shaped the work's goals. Following that, special observations are discussed.

4.8.1 Assumptions

The demand for digital media content delivery is rapidly expanding. This increased distribution will spread to 3D content, which now lacks the required copyright protection methods enjoyed by 2D content. The work in this thesis focuses on the use of watermarking for copyright protection as a solution to this challenge.

While a watermarking system cannot prevent copyright infringement, it can be used to identify users who redistribute information through unauthorized channels. The watermarking system must include an identifier for each active user on the distribution service in order to be functional. This method presupposes that each individual is given a separate identification number. As a safety precaution, a multiplier of five was set to accommodate for population increase and multiple accounts. While this is a high value, it has a significant overhead and ensures that no identification number collisions will occur in the near future. block-based watermarking systems are the only ones capable of retaining high robustness while providing a data payload that meets the requirements shows how stereoscopic picture pairs are used in existing 3D material. Despite its widespread popularity, this format has a far higher data requirement and shows the disparity map with the best compression ratio. As a result, disparity map estimation was used in the suggested watermarking strategy. As shown in [12], transforming depth map-based photos into disparity map-based images is an added benefit of such a system. Depth Map-based systems would benefit from smaller data sets than disparity maps as a result of this shift. The two submitted photos have already been corrected as a result of adapting existing information. This allows for a reduction in disparity map optimization, allowing for horizontal axis search.

4.8.2 Design Observations

The suggested system's primary goal is to be useable as a transaction tracking system. To do this, the proposed system must be resistant to a variety of attacks. As a result, the DCT transformation was applied. DCTs have a higher computational complexity than other watermarking systems. However, because of the system's complexity, it can apply spread spectrum techniques, which increases the embedded message's survival rate and reduces the ability of rogue users to elude detection.

When paired with the quantization matrix, the DCT transformation has the added benefit of combating JPEG compression. This is due to the proposed system's capacity to better counteract some of the losses that occur when photos are compressed with JPEG. The decision to utilize 8 by 8 block sizes to match the size of the quantization matrix was influenced by the use of DCT.

Because spread spectrum techniques were used in the detection procedure, it was evident that a correlation-based detector would yield the greatest results. There are three basic correlation functions that can be used: LC, NC, and CC are the three letters that make up the letters LC, NC, and CC. However, the LC function's broad detection zone causes false detection. The difficulty described above is overcome in NC; nevertheless, due to common image enhancing techniques such as biasing and histogram equalization, NC suffers from poor detection when the image is scaled. As a result, the only correlation capable of matching the requirements is the CC function.

Scrambling was employed to boost the system's robustness even more. The security and robustness against localized attacks are the two main advantages of such a system. The extra security comes from scrambling the message at random. Because the data is randomized, it will be extremely difficult for a bad user to discover the message and enter fraudulent information. However, enhanced robustness can only be attained when convolutional codes are used.

Dependent bits are prevented from occupying adjacent positions by spreading the information over the image in random sections. Because the damaged bits are scattered across the convolutional code, a potential localized assault will have a

small impact on the overall message. Another problem with the detection method is that some attacks reverse the embedded pattern's polarity. To fix this issue, polarity headers are needed. A large header increases the likelihood of success. A header of size seven was used for this project. By comparing the detected header with the embedded header (using the Hamming Distance metric), the polarity of the detected bits may be identified, and polarity reversal can be avoided. The suggested system's final flaw is its inability to differentiate between left and right images. Within the watermark detector, there are two detection paths to handle this problem. The first path assumes the picture is on the left, whereas the second assumes the image is on the right. The detector compares the CRC of the detected message to the CRC of the embedded message after decoding the embedded message. If the two messages are identical, the system assumes that the message was correctly detected.

Because the images lack a unique identity, the system is unable to distinguish between the two forms. The algorithm could compare the images to the original left image and make a decision based on the similarity of the two images. The technique described above, on the other hand, would increase the amount of data that the detector must keep. As a result, the data payload loss of sixteen bits is a smaller penalty.

4.9. Proposed Approach

We have designed a novel approach for watermark embedding using wavelet domain. Moreover, In our proposed model, we did out a 3 level decomposition on the blue component of an original image in DWT domain based on Haar wavelet. Our proposed framework consist of Harris detector which is used for the level 3 diagonal coefficient of image in order to extract the feature of an image and embed watermarking. Moreover, the proposed model use key dependent property which extract additional numbers of feature points that are generated from the existing feature points and the watermark is finally embedded into the extracted feature points. In order to get the copyright using watermark image a secret key is used with watermark images.

4.9.1 Embedding Technique

In this part, we discussed the embedding method, which is the method that is used for the feature point –based picture watermarking approach whenever there is an embedded watermark. Whenever there is an embedded watermark, this method is used. When using embedding techniques, the following is a list of the most

important aims that should be pursued:

- To conduct a three level DWT decomposition.
- By using a Harris Detector in order to get the feature points
- New feature points using a Key Dependent Algorithm.
- This approach provide the facility of Watermark Embedding in image.

4.9.2 Third level DWT decomposition

In order to get the watermarking of an image the proposed model uses the blue component of an original image using HW to decompose the image. From simulation results, it have been observed that the proposed embedding and watermarking approach provides high PSNR as compared to the benchmark models.

4.9.3 Extraction of the feature points

In order to extract the feature points a Harris detector algorithm consist of the following steps: 1) Compute x and y derivatives of original image I using a convolution kernel d_x and d_y . Let the derivatives be I_x and I_y .

2) Compute products of derivatives at each pixel.

$$I_x^2 = I_x * I_x; \text{-----} (1)$$

$$I_y^2 = I_y * I_y; \text{-----} (2)$$

$$I_{xy} = I_x * I_y; \text{-----} (3)$$

3) compute the sum of products of derivatives at each pixel using a Gaussian filter.

$$S_x^2 = G * I_x^2; \text{-----} (1)$$

$$S_y^2 = G * I_y^2; \text{-----} (2)$$

$$S_{xy} = G * I_{xy}; \text{-----} (3)$$

4) Compute the response of the detector at each pixel.

$$R = (S_x^2 * S_y^2 - S_{xy}^2) - k * (S_x^2 + S_y^2)^2;$$

5) Find out the points with large corner response function R ($R > \text{threshold}$).

6) Take the points of local maxima of R.

4.9.4. Watermark Embedding

The watermark bits are embedded into the feature points by the formula,

$$D3(x, y) = D3(x, y) + 0.15 * w(x_1, y_1);$$

x, y are the coordinates of the feature points

x_1, y_1 are the coordinates of the watermark

D3 is the level 3 diagonal coefficient

W is the watermark

Figure 7: Left image (Original), Right Image (Watermark)

4.9.5 Extraction Technique

In order to extract the watermark from the watermarked image require two things i.e. one is the secret key and second thing is the original image.

In order to perform the extraction process over watermarked image the following steps are important:

- 1) Using Harris detector in order to get the feature.
- 2) Using Key Dependent Algorithm in order to get new feature points.
- 3) Watermark extraction is done.

The proposed model perform 3-level decomposition on the blue components of original image and watermarked image. Moreover, in the second step it generate again all the feature points of the original image by repeating steps 1, 2 and 3

using the secret key. Then the watermark is extracted from the feature points of original image and the watermarked image by using the formula,

$$W(x1, y1) = (Dw3(x, y) - D3(x, y)) / 0.15;$$

x, y are the coordinates of the feature points

Dw3 is the level 3 diagonal coefficient of watermarked image

D3 is the level 3 diagonal coefficient of watermarked image

W is the watermark.

The original and extracted watermark is shown in figure 5 (left) and figure 5 (right) respectively.

Figure 8: Original and extracted watermark is shown in figure 6 (left) and figure 6 (right)

4.10 Watermark Characteristics

It is necessary to compare the suggested system's properties to those of similar 3D picture watermarking systems in order to evaluate it. Comparison of the proposed system with the works covered in Chapter 4's literature study. The suggested system is shown by the blue column. A green cell indicates that the planned system has improved, a yellow cell shows that it has not improved, and a red cell indicates that the intended system has acted badly in these conditions. Some of the data's properties are quantifiable, but just a handful of them are.

Because they describe the embedding site, the first three rows, which relate to the watermark features, are qualitative. The next three rows (Decoding Requirements) are numerical because they pertain to the amount of storage required to decode the watermark from the left image. Furthermore, data scalability is a qualitative feature that is established by assessing the proposed system's structure. Finally, the payload property is a qualitative as well as a quantitative quality. This metric's qualitative element pertains to the consistency of accessible bits from image to image. A quantitative portion of the attribute, on the other hand, refers to the average number of bits that can be embedded.

The system must retrieve information from the left and right images in order to achieve the transaction –tracking goal. As a result, the position of the watermark is the most important feature. The suggested system clearly outperforms the majority of the existing systems, as seen in the table. The proposed systems are the exceptions. However, there are a few disadvantages: (1) the need for decoding data, and (2) the data payload.

The amount of data required for extracting information from the received image is indicated by the decoding data need. In the data payload category, it can be shown that the suggested system does not outperform the stated work when compared to the work completed. However, when compared to the above –mentioned studies, the suggested system beats them in terms of decoding data requirements.

In comparison to the works, the proposed watermarking system provided no gain in terms of watermark position, but the decoding data need metric was compromised. However, when compared to previous work, the proposed system could store more data (data payload characteristic), achieving one of the proposed system's key goals. Finally, the system has greater scalability than the previous work [29]. The ability of a system to increase its data payload consistently as the resolution of the delivered image rises is referred to as scalability. When comparing the suggested system to the work in

[28], the proposed system shows an improvement in scalability. While the most important necessary category is an important part of the detecting process.

In conclusion, while the suggested system has significant flaws, it exceeds previous research in the areas required to prevent hostile users from successfully manipulating the transaction tracking system.

4.11 The novelty of the Proposed System

Various influences from existing literature were used to inspire the numerous components that were utilized when creating the suggested system. (1) Disparity map preprocessing, (2) HPDM, watermark techniques were the key components inspired by external sources. The work in provided the original motivation for the disparity map pre-processing. The lack of smoothness in the disparity map is the driving force behind the use of this method. When compared to the depth map, the disparity map's lack of homogeneity becomes apparent. In order to remedy this issue, the works were also used to help reduce the noise in the disparity map.

The work done impacted the design of the most important component of the system, namely HPDM. The work developed a system that embeds data into all accessible pixels. The approach identified the pixels that would be concealed and reduced the embedding intensities at certain spots to assist eliminate some of the distortion.

The rendering procedure was extended to the entire image in this thesis. The produced frame was then used to find the concealed pixels. A new disparity map was constructed using the rendered image's non-hidden pixels. The Hidden-Pixel Disparity Map is a new disparity map that can detect holes and blocking in images. This knowledge can be utilized to prevent the encoder from embedding data in such blocks. To retrieve the image, a simplified form of the HPDM, i.e., decision matrix, must be saved to detect the encoded message.

The encoder and decoder are the two main components of the watermarking process. These elements were influenced by a variety of sources. (1) spread spectrum addition, (2) quantization, (3) pattern formation, and (4) correlation was all inspired by other sources. The study given in [22] inspired the spread spectrum approach. However, because the method in [22] can only transfer one bit per image, the approach given in the paper had to be changed in this thesis.

The Quantization approach is quite common, and it was inspired by [35] and [36]'s work. The main distinction is that, whereas the studies in [35] and [36] do not reverse the quantization process, the work in this thesis does.

A better spread spectrum coding was required for pattern generation. As a result, the work in [23] was utilized to inform the selection of the best PNG generator. The correlation block was the final component that was inspired by an external source. The work done in [20] had an influence on it.

The majority of the above-mentioned affected components can be found in Chapter 4, as described below.

- Disparity Map Preprocessing, red
- HPDM, blue sub
- Spread Spectrum Addition, red sub
- Quantization, blue sub
- Pattern Generation, green sub
- Correlation, purple sub

Results and Evaluation

This chapter will look at some of the difficulties in detecting the watermarked pattern, as well as the theory behind the methods used to overcome them. The various types of attacks and metrics will be discussed in Section 5.1. Watermark robustness will be discussed in Section 5.2, and two methods for improving the watermarking system's performance will be proposed. Finally, Section 5.3 will go over some of the difficulties in verifying the authenticity of the detected watermark, as well as the recommended solution to the problem. The Tsukuba data set is also included in the Middlebury data set, which was used to create the various figures in this thesis. The first section will total the bit capacity of the various images (Tsukuba, Saw tooth, Venus, Bull, Poster, Barn1, and Barn2). The PSNR value of the images under various embedding strengths will be provided in the second section.

5.1 Watermark Attacks and Metrics

Watermarking's success is determined by its ability to withstand attacks. Any modification that can change the image or the watermark pattern is considered an attack. These attacks can be intentional, in which a malicious user attempts to remove embedded information, or unintentional, in which image enhancement techniques or transmission errors are used. As a result, the watermark should be resistant to deliberate attacks and image enhancement. Watermark attacks were classified into four types in [38]:

- Removal Attack
- Geometric Attack
- Cryptographic Attack
- Protocol Attack

Watermark removal attacks use image manipulation to remove the watermark. These operations either involve (1) Filtering or (2) noise addition. The goal of these attacks is to make it difficult to detect the watermark without jeopardizing its security.

In most cases, synchronization counter measures can be used to combat these attacks. By removing the watermark or deceiving the detector, cryptographic attacks attempt to breach security. Finally, in order to create ambiguity, protocol attacks try to add the attacker's watermark.

The system's robustness to removal attacks will be the focus of this thesis's test. Because each user receives a unique watermark pattern, protocol attacks are not a big deal for reference tracking. If the watermarked content contains multiple identifiers, it is safe to assume that both parties were involved in the copyright infringement. While geometric attacks affect the watermark, their impact on the 3D experience is unknown because the majority of the systems surveyed in Chapter 4 did not conduct such tests.

The following attacks were used to evaluate the system's performance:

- Salt and Pepper Noise Addition
- Gaussian Noise Addition
- Median Filtering
- Blurring Filter
- Salt and Pepper Noise Addition
- Sharpening Filter
- Histogram Equalization
- Cropping
- JPEG Compression

These eight methods will cover a significant portion of both intentional and unintentional attacks, and insight into the system’s robustness will be gained.

5.2 Watermark Robustness

The robustness of watermarking schemes is one factor to consider when categorizing them. As discussed in Section 5.2, the robustness of a watermark is defined as its ability to remain intact when subjected to signal distortion. Typically, a system's robustness is classified as 1) fragile: the inability to survive distortion; 2) Semi –Fragile: the ability to survive a limited amount of distortion; or 3) Robust: the ability to survive most signal distortion. It is difficult to design a watermarking scheme that can withstand all signal distortions of varying intensities. This watermarking scheme's intended application is transaction tracking to ensure that malicious users (Example in 1.1) cannot remove the watermark; thus, robustness enhancement techniques must be used. Two methods were used to help with this process.

5.3 Convolutional Code

The robustness of watermarking schemes is one factor to consider when classifying them. As discussed in Section 5.1, a watermark's robustness is defined as its ability to remain intact when subjected to signal distortion. Normally, a system's robustness is classified as either high or low. 1) Fragile: unable to stand on one's own two feet. The various attacks described in Section 5.1 target the watermark pattern, causing the detector to misinterpret the embedded data. An error correcting code can be used to correct the detected message to combat this issue. Error correction can be accomplished by incorporating redundancy into the data and bypassing it via an encoder. In most cases, the encoder will produce multiple outputs; p_i . Convolutional codes were used in this thesis.

Figure 7 depicts the two main representations for convolutional codes.

Figure 7 (a) shows a block diagram of the encoder, while Figure 7 (b) shows a state machine representation of the convolutional code. While there are many different generator polynomials, not all of them have good error –correcting properties.

Figure 9: (a) Block Diagram of Convolutional Code, (b) State Machine Representation of Convolutional Code

To decode convolutional codes, the most basic method is to generate all possible combinations and compare the distance between the generated output and the received signal. The Hamming distance, from [40], is commonly used to calculate the distance between two sequences. This value usually indicates how many bits must be substituted to make one sequence look like the other. The main disadvantage of this method is that as the complexity of the code increases, so does the time required to decode the sequence—for every extra bit, the number of comparisons doubles. Viterbi decoders are used to address this issue.

Each state is treated as a node in the algorithm, and the Viterbi decoder branches into two new paths at each node. The Hamming distance of each path is calculated as the decoder creates more paths. On rare occasions, two paths will meet at the same node. When this happens, the decoder will select the path with the shortest Hamming distance and discard the other. It keeps branching the paths until the paths are the same size as the received message.

Figure 10: Viterbi Decoder Branching

The decoder compares the Hamming distances of all paths once more and selects the path with the lowest Hamming distance as the output. The benefit of this method is that, unlike the brute-force method, the decoder deletes paths as they become obvious.

5.4 Scrambling

Scrambling is commonly used to improve the watermark's resistance to localized attacks. The scrambling can be used in one of two places: (1) the image or (2) the message. While image scrambling is more resistant to cropping attacks, it is not a viable option for the watermarking system used in this thesis. Scrambling is typically a pre-processing step used prior to embedding the watermark. This causes the pixels in the image plane to be scrambled. As a result, if a localized attack, such as a cropping attack, is ever used, the damaged pixels will have little effect on watermark detection. While the entire block is damaged, the scrambling spreads pixels across multiple blocks, reducing the overall system's impact. This is the most robust approach, but it is also not feasible for the system described here because the actual pixel locations would be marred by the shifting caused by the image rendering process.

5.5 Message Authentication

```

1  Let B represent input bit message
2  Let CS represent size of CRC
3  Let P , represent the CRC Polynomial
4  BA = B appended with CS zeroes
5  for i = 1 to Length of B
6  if ([i] equals 0)
7  Do Nothing
8  else
9  for k = 1 to CS
10  BA [i + k - 1] = BA [i + k - 1] ⊕ P[i + k - 1 ] mod 2
11  end for
12  end if
13  end for
14  return the Last CS bit of BA
    
```

Algorithm: CRC Code Generation Algorithm

5.6 Block Diagram

To avoid false detections, the watermark detection process typically applies a threshold to the correlation. Nonetheless, the possibility of false detection remains. Verifying that the extracted message is correct is a major challenge in watermark detection. If a watermark decoder is used on a non –watermarked image, there is no way to validate the extracted message. This thesis, like the work in [31], used Cyclical Redundancy Codes (CRC) to combat this problem.

Figure 11: Block Diagram of CRC check

5.7 CRC Code Generation

In this thesis, CRC codes are used to detect errors. CRC codes were implemented using a single –wire implementation. The following errors can be detected using this code: (1) Any message with an odd number of bit errors, (2) all double – bit errors, (3) consecutive errors within windows equal to or smaller than the CRC size, and (4) Large Clusters of Errors. A polynomial divisor is used in the CRC calculation. The bit divisor can be represented in two ways: as a bit string (1001), or as a number.

The second method is to write $x^4 + 1$ as a polynomial. The method for calculating the CRC value of a message is shown in Figure 5.3, which uses the polynomial $x^8 + x^5 + x^4 + 1$ as the input.5.1; this process is illustrated below

5. 8 Bit Capacity

Table 1: Bit Capacity of the Image

Bit Capacity	SSD	ZSSD	LSSSD	SGRAD	SAD	ZSAD	LSSAD	NCC	ZNCC	MSE	Theoretical Limit
Tsukuba	799	850	859	981	665	835	831	849	778	850	1728
Saw tooth	2063	2057	2055	2108	2087	2093	2092	2051	2056	2057	2538
Venus	2052	2054	2049	2072	1993	2052	2050	2064	2077	2054	2538
Bull	2188	2217	2213	2192	2155	2208	2213	2221	2207	2217	2538
Poster	1926	1944	1991	1976	1879	1964	1962	2030	2024	1994	2538
Barn1	2024	2110	2123	2142	1976	2105	2117	2127	2113	2110	2538
Barn2	2189	2237	2237	2171	2164	2227	2223	2234	2201	2237	2538

The bit capacity of each image for the proposed system, as well, as how these results vary with various cost functions, should be evaluated first. The bit analysis results show that the method for generating the disparity map used in this thesis has a significant impact on the system's bit capacity. Most of the images that used the SGRAD also had the best bit storage performance, according to the results. As a result, for the remainder of the tests, the disparity map method will be used.

The high fluctuations in bit efficient percentage are another notable phenomenon that can be seen (the number of embeddable bits divided by the theoretical limit). Because of the scene's complexity, it is particularly noticeable in the Tsukuba data. Consider dividing the scene into two depth levels (for simplicity) during the rendering process: the foreground layer and the background layer. Objects in the foreground will overlap and cover objects in the background in this case, resulting in an increase in the number of pixels that are invisible. The number of places where pixels can be embedded will be reduced. The number of hidden pixels grows in lockstep with the number of objects in the foreground.

This problem is further exacerbated by an increase in the number of disparity layers within the image. While the number of embedding locations can be decreased by reducing the number of conditions set when generating the decision matrix, it would require a larger embedding strength and significantly reduce the fidelity of the image.

Figure 12: (a) Original Two Layer Image,

(b) Rendered Two Layer Image

5.9 Filtering Attacks

Some image modification techniques were used to test the system's robustness once more. Three filter attacks were carried out. The first was median filtering, which is a popular technique for removing additive impulsive noise. Average filtering is the name given to the second filtering attack. It is a popular noise removal method that effectively removes Gaussian white noise.

Table 2: Filter Attacks

Filter Attack	Median 3x3	Median 5x5	Blurring 3x3	Blurring 5x5	Sharpening 3x3	Sharpening 5x5
Tsukuba	0.44	0.89	0	0	0	0
saw tooth	11.36	1.03	5.37	0	0	0
Venus	9.92	2.27	7.43	0	0	0
Bull	6.23	0	0	0	0	0
Poster	24.94	7.93	29.25	0.22	0	0
Barn1	21.69	2.47	23.55	0	0	0
Barn2	17.20	0	2.08	0	0	0

The sharpening filter was the third filtering attack used. Table 2 shows that the watermarking scheme is more resistant to filtering attacks with larger mark sizes. Although the results varied depending on the image, it is clear that they could be improved by increasing the size of the embedded mark or the embedding strength of the watermark pattern.

5.10 Miscellaneous Attacks

The final tests that must be completed do not fall into either of the previous two categories, but they will be discussed in this section. Histogram Equalization is the first attack. It had no effect on the detected message, as expected. The second attack, image cropping, attempted to detect the image by removing about 10% of the pixels in the image from one of the four sides of the image using message scrambling and Viterbi decoding. Finally, the watermarked image was compressed using JPEG to test the system's resistance to compression attacks. The results of these attacks are presented in Table 3. This table shows that the system can withstand cropping and histogram attacks while still being able to compress JPEG files. This shows that the proposed system is reliable and capable of withstanding the majority of these attacks.

Table 3: Miscellaneous Attacks

Misc. Attacks	Histogram Equalization	Crop Upper	Crop Lower	Crop Left	Crop Right	Jpeg 40	Jpeg 60	Jpeg 80
Tsukuba (Left)	0	0	0	0	0	13.33	0	0
saw tooth (Left)	0	0	0	0	0	3.71	0	0
Venus (Left)	0	0	0	0	0	22.93	0	0
Bull (Left)	0	0	0	0	0	20.41	0	0
Poster (Left)	0	0	0	0	0	1.85	0	0
Barn1 (Left)	0	0	0	0	0	8.50	0	0
Barn2 (Left)	0	0	0	0	0	1.58	0	0

Table 3 represent the statically analysis of the misc. Attacks over the watermarked image. These miscellaneous attacks are mentioned in the table. Moreover, the parameters that are associated with the features of image represent the resistant to attack's

Figure 13: Simulations results using the proposed algorithms (Left Image)

Figure.13 represent the simulation results show the left image features extracted through watermark embedding.

Figure 14: Image after reconstructions

Figure.14 represent the image after reconstruction. In Figure.12, we can observe the accuracy and the resistant of the proposed model to JPEG compression and other attacks.

Figure 15: Ground truth disparity (map)

Figure.15 represents the ground truth disparity map achieved from the original image source using the proposed model.

Figure 16: Simulations results for hidden pixel results (Right) and decision matrix (Right)

In Figure.16, we carried out simulation results based on the proposed 3D image watermarking. The hidden pixel shows in the right image represent the watermarking in the image. The image at the right side represent the decision matrix of the proposed model using feature-embedding techniques.

Figure 17: Watermarked image

Figure.17, show the watermarked image using middle –frequency techniques.

Figure 18: Error Signal Right

In Figure.18, we used the JPEG compression attack using Adobe CS5. As, the proposed model using secure algorithm that cannot be penetrated by these attacks and it is very difficult to retrieve the secret key information as well.

5.11 Experimental Results

This section provides the experimental results of our proposed watermarking scheme. The algorithm has been implemented using Matlab7. Rest of the section is characterized into:

- Performance Evaluation without attacks.
- Watermark Extraction from various attacks.
- Performance Evaluation with attacks.

5.11.1. Performance Evaluation without attacks

For this evaluation, we have taken the images Lena, Baboon, Airfield, and Peppers as shown below. On every image, the proposed watermarking technique is performed and then the respective PSNR value of the image is calculated by comparing the watermarked image with its original image. The results of the evaluation are shown in the following

tables.

Lena

Baboon

Airfield

Peppers

Figure 19: Results after using the propose Model based on different images

Figure.19, present the simulations results using the proposed approach. The images describes different structure and background in order to test the proposed model.

Figure 20: Simulation results after watermarking using the proposed framework

Figure.20 represents the simulation results after watermarking using the proposed model.

Figure 21: Simulation results of the proposed framework

Figure.21 represent the simulation results based on different images and the PSNR using 256 bits, 512 bits and 1024 bits.

Table 4. Shows the simulations results and statistical values obtained during the experiments.

Table 4: Simulations results using proposed model

Images	PSNR Values
Lena	38.9119
Baboon	36.8103
Airfield	38.3127
Peppers	38.1698

Table 4 represent various attack analysis such as compression attack as well as background noise.

Table 5. Attack Analysis of the proposed model

Lena Attacks	PSNR Values
JPEG compression 1:19	32.4393
Gaussian Noise (2%)	32.9937
Sharpen Edges	35.1832
Uniform Noise (2%)	35. 5392
Salt & Pepper Noise (0.001)	33.5771
Poisson Noise	28.0450
Sparkle Noise (0.001)	35.0616

5.11.2 Watermark Extraction from various attacks

We used the Lena image to present the results of the watermark extraction. Moreover, in order to evaluate the attack resistance of the proposed model we used Lena image and the watermark all these attacks are simulated using Matlab7. After each attack, the watermark is extracted by the proposed technique.

Figure 22: Simulations represent original images and the watermark to be embedded

The original image as well as the watermark that will be incorporated into the image are shown in Figure.22 Figure 22 (left) and Figure 22 (right) show the original Lena image, which was 512 pixels wide by 512 pixels tall, and the original watermark, respectively (right). The numerous attacks that were tested, together with the photos that were attacked and the watermark that was kept, are displayed below.

Various Attacks Tested:

Figure 23: Various Attack tested such Rotation by 60° and scaling at 2:1

Figure.23 illustrates the results that occurred as a result of the proposed model being attacked in a variety of different ways. Scaling and rotation by a factor of 60 are also incorporated into these assaults. It was found out that the newly proposed model performs more effectively than the models that already exist, and this was established based on the findings of the trials that were done.

Figure 24: JPEG Compression by 1:19 Gaussian noise of mean and Variance 0.5

Figure.24 present simulation results after scaling, rotation, JPEG Compression and Gaussian noise of mean and variance.

Figure 25: Salt & Pepper Noise of noise Extracted Watermark Density 0.2

Figure 26: Integer image and its histogram in order to verify the error and the background noise in the watermarked image

Figure 27: Watermark Image thresholding using float image and its histogram

Image to be Hidden

Histogram of image to be hidden

Hidden Image Thresholded at 70

Figure28: Hidden pixel in watermark images

Figure 29: Insertion of hidden image in the watermarked image

Figure 30: Watermark recovery from the watermarked image without noise using the proposed model

5.11.3. Performance Evaluation with attacks

In order to test the security aspect of the proposed model we test a few attacks and the PSNR value were recorded in the table. The PSNR values are shown in Table 6. All these attacks are performed using Adobe Photoshop CS3.

Table 6. Attacks on Images and the PSNR values

Lena Attacks	PSNR Values
JPEG compression 1:19	32.4393
Gaussian Noise (2%)	32.9937
Sharpen Edges	35.1832
Uniform Noise (2%)	35. 5392
Salt & Pepper Noise (0.001)	33.5771
Poisson Noise	28.0450
Sparkle Noise (0.001)	35.0616

Conclusion and Future work

Conclusion

A method for determining the distortion induced by disparity –based image rendering was implemented in this thesis. Three theory –based chapters were presented before the suggested system was presented. The first few chapters laid the groundwork for the rest of the book. Recognize the mechanisms of picture watermarking and disparity map estimation. A summary of the situation to highlight the value of 3D picture watermarking, recent work was presented. Researchers in this field have employed a variety of tactics. A few strategies for increasing toughness were created in order to overcome some of the flaws in current watermarking techniques. A mechanism for detecting rendering effects was added, and the two were integrated to form a strong watermarking system. The rendering prediction technique was shown to be able to counteract the effects of disparity map rendering in the tests reported in this thesis since no difference between the left and right images was detected when rendered.

The suggested system's bit capacity ranged from 38 percent to 88 percent. Two reasons are responsible for this variation. First, as the number of items in the scene grows, so does the depth map's complexity. As the complexity of the decision matrix grows, the number of occluded pixels grows, lowering the amount of space available in the decision matrix. The cost function utilized was the second aspect that influenced this figure. The image smoothness is determined by the cost function of choosing. The available space grows as the smoothness of the disparity map increases due to the limits placed on it, yet the fidelity of the watermarked image behaved as expected. The process was applied to the image block when the embedding strength was set to zero.

Salt and pepper sounds were not a problem for the system. However, it was not as successful against Gaussian noise. Most of the attacks made sure that the PSNR between the watermark picture and the attack image was larger than 35 dB to help achieve realistic results. However, because of the image's great fluctuation, staying over the 35 dB level was unachievable. The system was able to withstand normal filtering attempts, which is the most intriguing finding. It was more resistant to bigger filter sizes, although it had the most trouble defeating median attacks.

The system was able to overcome histogram equalization and cropping thanks to some robustness –enhancing strategies. When JPEG compression was used, however, a bit error rate of about 9% was recorded. Other than that, the mechanism could survive other compression ratios. This can be traced to the watermarking process's quantization stage. Embedding watermark in Left and Right Image, reducing necessary information for the extraction process, and Predicting distortion to reduce watermark damage were all capabilities of the system demonstrated in this thesis when compared to existing disparity map based watermarking systems.

MATLAB was used to build and test the suggested system. The proposed system may withstand image –based rendering as well as a few watermark attacks, according to the results of the experiments. The Middlebury data set as well as the Tsukuba data set were used in the testing. The testing was restricted to smaller images due to the computationally demanding nature of disparity map imaging. The usage of parallel processors, such as GPUs, can improve the temporal performance of the disparity map estimation procedure dramatically.

Future work

This thesis concentrated on the watermarking process, leaving out some of the more advanced rendering techniques, such as whole –filling in the generated image. The hole –filling technique would not have affected watermark identification because of the limits imposed on the decision matrix. Future research in this area could loosen the restrictions in order to develop a mechanism that can withstand such attacks.

Another interesting finding obtained during this study is that the background accounts for 43-55% of the pixels in the test image. The cropped image can be scrambled and the resultant image can be watermarked if the decision matrix is used to identify background pixels after the non –background pixels are deleted. Once the image is unscrambled, the non –background pixels are reintroduced into the image. This is comparable to a white Gaussian noise attack.

The a foresaid system could be realized and give increased performance by developing a watermarking scheme that can withstand strong Gaussian attacks, resulting in a robust and blind watermarking technique that decreases the overall amount of information necessary for the extraction process.

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